

Integration of Project-Based Learning (PjBL) and Gamification Models to Improve Student Motivation and Critical Thinking Skills

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Abstract

The 21st century learning requires students to master communication, collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking skills (4Cs). In the context of the Merdeka Curriculum, Project-Based Learning (PjBL) is one of the recommended learning models for developing these skills through authentic project-based activities. However, the implementation of PjBL in schools still faces various obstacles, such as low student motivation, a passive learning culture, and limited cognitive involvement of students during the inquiry process. These conditions prevent the goal of developing critical thinking skills from being optimally achieved. Meanwhile, gamification has emerged as an approach that can increase student motivation, focus, and participation through the application of game elements such as points, challenges, levels, and rewards. This article aims to analyze the potential of integrating PjBL and Gamification as an innovative learning model to increase student learning motivation and critical thinking skills. The research was conducted through a conceptual review and literature study of various studies on the effectiveness of PjBL, Gamification, and 21st-century learning. The results of the study show that PjBL is capable of training critical thinking skills through the process of authentic problem solving, but its success is highly dependent on the level of student motivation and engagement. The integration of Gamification has been proven to strengthen intrinsic motivation, increase cognitive engagement, and encourage active student participation throughout the project process. In addition, structured game elements can be incorporated into each stage of the project to foster a sense of competence, challenge, and reward that supports higher-level thinking activities. The integration of these two approaches also enables the creation of a more interactive, adaptive learning environment that is in line with the characteristics of digital native students who need continuous stimulation. Thus, the integrative PjBL–Gamification model has the potential to be a more effective, enjoyable, and relevant learning approach for the characteristics of digital era students and is in line with the principles of the Merdeka Curriculum.

Keywords: Project-Based Learning, Gamification, learning motivation, critical thinking, 21st-century learning.

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, students are required to master communication, collaboration, creativity, and critical thinking skills, often referred to as the 4Cs. The 4Cs are basic skills that students must possess in order to survive and be competitive in the face of rapid developments in science and technology in the current era (Septikasari, R., & Frasandy, 2018). In the current Indonesian education curriculum, the Merdeka Curriculum, the learning process is emphasized to be more flexible and student-oriented, making the development of 4C skills crucial. However, current classroom conditions show that student motivation to learn tends to decline, while distractions from digital technology are increasing, causing many challenges for exploration-based learning processes.

Digital distractions, such as the use of digital devices for non-academic activities during learning, have a significant impact on students' focus and motivation, with technology contributing

to approximately 51.95% of learning concentration disruption (Martin et al., 2025). In addition, the Project-Based Learning (PjBL) model has been identified as the primary method for improving critical thinking skills, although its implementation is often less than optimal due to a passive learning culture and the tendency of students to accept instructions without asking critical questions. The habit of obeying and following instructions is one of the main obstacles in developing students' critical thinking skills in the classroom (Maro, 2014). Students tend to accept instructions at face value, so they are less motivated to analyze and ask critical questions, which are core aspects of project-based learning. Meanwhile, gamification has been proven to increase student motivation, focus, and engagement through fun game elements (Fitriana & Maro, 2018).

Recent reviews of research show that combining gamification elements with Project-Based Learning not only increases student motivation and engagement in learning activities, but also contributes to the development of higher-order thinking skills and knowledge absorption. Literature analysis indicates that project-based learning models equipped with game elements can create a more memorable and meaningful learning experience for students. This also encourages them to engage in a more active investigation process compared to traditional methods (Huang et al., 2023).

Conceptually, the development of critical thinking skills does not only depend on the learning model applied, but also on how the learning experience is organized to encourage continuous cognitive engagement of students. The 4C skills cannot develop optimally if students are only seen as recipients of information, without room for exploration, reflection, and independent understanding building (Septikasari, R., & Frasandy, 2018). This condition requires learning that is not only oriented towards the final result but also towards the thinking process experienced by students during the learning process. In practice, learning that is too monotonous and lacks variety in activities tends to reduce interest in learning, so that students are less motivated to think critically and creatively.

In addition, the characteristics of students in the digital age show a decline in concentration skills and an increasing need for interactive and contextual learning. Digital distractions have a major impact on students' focus and motivation to learn, especially when learning activities fail to match the appeal of the technology they encounter in their daily lives (Martin et al., 2025). Therefore, an adaptive learning approach is needed, one that can take advantage of the characteristics of digital native students and provide a learning experience that is both challenging and enjoyable. This kind of approach is expected to not only maintain students' focus, but also encourage them to actively engage in higher-level thinking processes. Therefore, the integration of PjBL and Gamification can be an innovative solution to strengthen student motivation while maximizing the development of critical thinking skills in line with the demands of 21st century learning.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The issues discussed in this article focus on the implementation of Project-Based Learning (PjBL) in schools today, as well as the various obstacles that arise during its implementation, especially those related to student motivation and a passive learning culture. Although PjBL has been recommended in the Merdeka Curriculum as one of the approaches to developing 21st-century skills, its implementation in the field has not been fully maximized. Many schools still treat projects as mere final assignments without integrating a deep inquiry process, thus failing to achieve the PjBL goal of developing higher-order thinking skills. This situation is exacerbated by a student learning culture that focuses more on compliance than independent exploration, making students less inclined to ask questions, engage in discussion, and express ideas critically.

Therefore, this article questions why PjBL, which has been used, has not been able to maximally develop students' critical thinking skills in accordance with the demands of 21st-century

learning and mastery of 4C skills, especially in the context of cognitive engagement and students' courage in expressing ideas. Low learning motivation, a lack of initiative among students in conducting independent analysis, and a tendency to avoid intellectual challenges indicate that the implementation of PjBL still needs to be strengthened in terms of pedagogical strategies that can stimulate active participation. In addition, the lengthy and demanding project process often causes boredom if it is not supported by an attractive learning design that is relevant to the characteristics of students in the digital age.

In this context, gamification is evaluated as an alternative approach that has the potential to increase student enthusiasm, concentration, and participation during the PjBL process. This approach is considered capable of providing stimuli, challenges, and faster feedback, thereby motivating students to be more active in each stage of the project. Game elements can serve as reinforcements in the investigation process and increase students' sense of competence, autonomy, and cognitive engagement. Based on these various issues, this article formulates questions about how an integrative PjBL-Gamification model can be designed and implemented as a more effective learning model to support the development of students' critical thinking skills and 4C competencies in line with the characteristics of 21st-century learning.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study applies a literature review approach by analyzing various journal articles, scientific books, and research reports related to the use of Project-Based Learning (PjBL) and Gamification in the context of 21st-century learning. This method was chosen to gain an in-depth understanding of the effectiveness of these two learning models in improving students' critical thinking skills and learning motivation, especially in relation to the Merdeka Curriculum. The analysis in this study focused on two main aspects, namely (1) students' critical thinking skills and (2) students' learning motivation. These two aspects were chosen based on the demands of 21st-century skills and the empirical conditions of learning in schools, which still face problems of low cognitive engagement and motivation among students.

This study also reviews the results of recent research showing a close relationship between PjBL and gamification in the context of language learning and education in general. Various studies on educational models have shown that the integrated application of gamification in PjBL can increase student engagement in learning and academic outcomes, particularly through the use of coordinated feedback and reward systems (Fazarini et al., 2024). In the Project-Based Learning (PjBL) model, the study focuses on the role of projects as a means of developing critical thinking skills through inquiry stages that include problem formulation, project planning, independent investigation, information processing, and presentation of results. PjBL is understood as a learning model that encourages students to think analytically, evaluate information, and make decisions based on empirical evidence. Students' active participation in making decisions throughout the project contributes significantly to the development of their critical and reflective thinking skills (Maro & Nurbatra, 2013). In addition, PjBL is also analyzed from the perspective of student learning motivation, particularly in relation to students' perseverance, activeness, and sense of responsibility during the project process. Although PjBL has great potential to foster intrinsic motivation, a number of studies state that projects that are time-consuming and complex can reduce motivation if they are not supported by an interesting and relevant learning design. Passive learning habits and dependence on teacher guidance can reduce students' cognitive participation in project-based learning (Maro, 2014).

Meanwhile, in the Gamification approach, the study focuses on the use of game elements such as point systems, levels, challenges, badges, and rewards as strategies to increase student motivation to learn. Gamification is analyzed as an approach that can create a fun, competitive, and

challenging learning experience, thereby encouraging students to be more actively involved in the learning process. The use of game elements in learning can increase student participation, focus, and activity, which ultimately supports the development of critical thinking skills (Fitriana & Maro, 2018). In addition, when linked to critical thinking skills, gamification is evaluated as a tool that can package problem-based challenges in such a way that motivates students to analyze situations, develop strategies, and evaluate the results achieved. Well-designed gamification has the potential to increase intrinsic motivation, a sense of competence, and cognitive engagement of students through valuable learning experiences (Deterding et al., 2011).

Thus, this literature review method allows the author to compare and integrate research findings related to PjBL and Gamification, particularly in relation to the development of students' critical thinking skills and learning motivation. The results of this analysis are then used as the basis for formulating an integrative PjBL-Gamification model that is relevant and feasible to be applied in 21st-century learning in the Merdeka Curriculum.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

No	Aspect		Key Findings	Implications	
	PjBL	Gamification		PjBL	Gamification
1.	Authentic project-based inquiry process	Challenging elements in learning	PjBL effectively trains critical thinking if inquiry runs optimally and is supported by motivation.	Teachers need to guide the inquiry process so that it is not reduced to a final assignment.	The challenge of helping students stay focused and interested throughout the project process
2.	Passive learning culture in project implementation	Reward system to increase participation	Low motivation and a passive culture hinder the effectiveness of PjBL	PjBL needs to be designed to be more participatory and reflective.	Rewards encourage students to ask questions and argue more actively.
3.	Long-term project process	Points, levels, and quick feedback	Gamification increases intrinsic motivation in the PjBL process	The project can be maintained until completion without burnout.	Points and levels maintain student enthusiasm throughout the project
4.	Discussion and exploration of ideas during the project	Interactivity and healthy competition	Students' cognitive engagement increases	Project discussions become more lively and analytical	Healthy competition encourages courage to

					express opinions
5.	Real-world context-based problem solving	Interactive learning design	An integrative model tailored to the characteristics of digital native students	PjBL becomes more relevant to students' lives	Gamification overcomes digital distractions
6.	Stages from planning to project presentation	Integration of game elements at each stage	The integration of PjBL– Gamification strengthens the inquiry process	Each stage of the project encourages analysis and reflection	Elemen permainan menjaga konsistensi keterlibatan
7.	Development of critical thinking skills	Problem-based challenges and rewards	Critical thinking develops gradually	Argumentation and evaluation are reinforced through projects	The challenge of increasing cognitive engagement

The results of the study show that the implementation of Project-Based Learning (PjBL) has great potential in developing students' critical thinking skills, especially when projects are designed based on authentic problems that are relevant to real life. Through the stages of planning, investigation, information processing, and presentation of results, students are encouraged to analyze problems, evaluate various sources of information, and make decisions based on evidence. Project-Based Learning (PjBL) is effective in training higher-order thinking skills when the inquiry process runs optimally (Maro & Nurbatra, 2013). However, in practice at school, PjBL is often turned into a mere final assignment without a good thinking process, so that the goal of developing critical thinking skills is not optimally achieved.

In addition, low student motivation is one of the main obstacles in the implementation of PjBL. When students lack strong intrinsic motivation, they often take a minimalist approach to projects, focusing only on completing tasks rather than exploring ideas and solving problems in depth. This condition is reinforced by a passive learning culture, such as obedience and deference, which is still commonly found in classrooms and makes students reluctant to ask questions, argue, or criticize the opinions of teachers or friends (Maro, 2014). As a result, the level of cognitive engagement of students becomes low, and project-based learning loses its meaning as a means of developing critical thinking skills.

The integration of gamification in PjBL appears promising as an effective solution to overcome existing problems. Gamification allows the learning process to be packaged in the form of challenges, role-playing, point systems, and rewards that can increase student motivation and active involvement. By incorporating game elements at each stage of the project, students are not only inspired to complete tasks, but they can also enjoy the learning process and dare to try new ideas. The application of gamification in learning can increase student participation, activity, and courage in expressing ideas, which are important prerequisites for the development of critical thinking skills (Fitriana & Maro, 2018). In addition to promoting motivation and engagement in learning, gamification also affects students' memory. A literature review reveals that the use of game elements in learning can help students retain information longer because the learning process is

active and enjoyable. Gamification encourages deeper cognitive engagement, thereby improving memory and understanding of the concepts being learned (Dewi et al., 2024).

These findings are consistent with empirical studies showing that students in English language learning contexts respond positively to the use of gamified activities, particularly in terms of motivation, engagement, and vocabulary acquisition. This supports the view that the application of gamification can improve the quality of learning experiences from an affective and cognitive perspective when combined with Project-Based Learning (PjBL) (Azzahra & Kembaren, 2025). Furthermore, gamification can increase students' intrinsic motivation through a sense of achievement, competence, and emotional engagement in learning activities (Deterding et al., 2011). In the context of PjBL, these elements act as reinforcers of the inquiry process, keeping students focused and motivated throughout the relatively long project process. This is particularly relevant given the nature of 21st-century students, who tend to have short attention spans and are easily distracted by digital technology.

Thus, the integration of PjBL and gamification not only serves as a strategy to increase learning motivation, but also as a pedagogical approach that can strengthen students' critical thinking processes in a sustainable manner. This model allows students to be actively involved not only in completing the final project product, but also in the inquiry, analysis, and reflection processes during the learning process. With this approach, the learning process becomes more meaningful because students are invited to engage cognitively, socially, and emotionally. This is in line with the principles of the Merdeka Curriculum, which emphasizes student-centered learning that is relevant to real life.

The PjBL-Gamification integration system works by connecting each stage of Project-Based Learning (PjBL) to specially designed game elements that increase student cognitive engagement. In the problem formulation stage, students are challenged to identify and formulate authentic problems, where they earn points based on the relevance and depth of the questions they ask. During the investigation and information analysis stage, students are challenged through a level system to critically select, evaluate, and process various sources before reaching a conclusion. Then, in the presentation and discussion stage of the project results, rewards are given to students who are able to defend their arguments well, provide constructive feedback, and reflect on the learning process that has been undertaken. With this system, students' critical thinking skills are developed gradually and continuously throughout the project.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the literature analysis that has been conducted, it can be concluded that Project-Based Learning (PjBL) is a learning model that has great potential in developing students' critical thinking skills. This is achieved through a process of inquiry, problem solving, and evidence-based decision making. However, the implementation of PjBL in schools still faces several obstacles, mainly related to low student motivation, a passive learning culture, and the dominance of the teacher's role, which limits student involvement in higher-level thinking processes.

The integration of gamification in PjBL has proven to be a solution to these problems by providing a more engaging, challenging, and motivating learning experience. Game elements such as points, challenges, levels, and rewards not only increase student motivation and focus but also encourage cognitive engagement, courage to express opinions, and collaboration among students. Thus, gamification acts as a reinforcement of the inquiry process in PjBL so that learning is not only oriented towards the final project outcome but also towards the critical thinking process experienced by students.

Therefore, the integrative PjBL-Gamification model can be seen as a relevant learning model that should be applied in the Merdeka Curriculum. This model is in line with learning needs in the 21st century, especially in developing 4C skills and characteristics of students in the digital age. It is hoped that the application of this model can facilitate teachers in creating more meaningful learning experiences, encourage students' enthusiasm for learning, and continuously hone their critical thinking skills.

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